

High performance thin layer chromatography of asiaticoside in *Centella asiatica*

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A high performance thin layer chromatography method, suitable for mass screening of plant samples for the quantitation of active saponin, asiaticoside, from *Centella asiatica* has been developed. Quantitation was performed in absorption-reflection mode at 620 nm by scanning the HPTLC plate ⁶⁰F₂₅₄ (mobile phase ethyl acetate-methanol-water, 60 : 12 : 8) after a colour development by vanillin-H₂SO₄ reagent.

Centella asiatica (L.) Umbelliferae, a weakly aromatic-smelling plant native to parts of India, China, Sri Lanka, Indonesia, Australia and Southern and Central Africa¹², has been utilised as a medicine in India since prehistoric time³. Fresh extract of the plant has been used for medicinal purposes by the people of Java and other Icelands for the healing of wounds and relief leprosy. The plant extract has been incorporated into the Indian pharmacopoeia² and recommended not only for wound healing but specially for the treatment of skin lesions and diseases such as lupus, eczema, leproxy and psoriasis. In addition *C. asiatica* has been used against diarrhoea, fever and diseases of female genital and urinary organs. The triterpenoid compounds apparently represent the chief pharmacologically active material in *C. asiatica*⁴. Asiaticoside, a trisaccharide triterpene, has been identified as the most active compound in the plant. Many commercial drug preparations of *C. asiatica* are available in West Germany and France⁵. The drug is reported to possess antiepilepsy activity⁶ and immunomodulatory properties⁷. A plant breeding programme to select *C. asiatica* variants rich in asiaticoside needed a quick, accurate and economical analytical procedure for the estimation of asiaticoside in the extract of individual plants. A direct coupling of high speed counter current chromatography to TLC has been used for the separation of asiaticoside from other saponins⁸. Recently, we have reported a reverse phase high performance liquid chromatography method for the estimation of asiaticoside in *C. asiatica*⁹. Due to its simplicity, accuracy and low cost than HPLC, high performance thin layer chromatography (HPTLC) is now utilized frequently in rapid screening of medicinal plants¹⁰. Here, a rapid and sensitive HPTLC procedure for the estimation of asiaticoside in *C. asiatica* plant extract is described. The results have been compared with HPLC results and the method is found suitable for rapid

screening of plant materials for their genotypic assessment without any special sample pretreatment.

Results and Discussion

Mobile phases of different solvent strength were used and a mixture of ethyl acetate-methanol-water (60 : 12 : 8) was found suitable for the separation of asiaticoside in *C. asiatica* plant extract. The developing reagent used for giving a stable blue colouration to asiaticoside was vanillin-sulphuric acid-ethanol (1 g : 5 ml : 95 ml). Peak corresponding to asiaticoside was at R_f 0.52 (Fig. 1). Peak purity test of asiaticoside was done by comparing visual spectra of asiaticoside in standard and sample tracks (Fig. 2). The calibration graph of asiaticoside was linear in the range 1–20 μ g; $Y = 134.75X + 2.0751$ ($r = 1.000$). For the estimation of recovery (98%), known amounts of stock solution of pure asiaticoside was added to *C. asiatica* plant extract and quantitative analysis was repeated thrice.

Fig. 1. HPTLC separation of asiaticoside (A) in *C. asiatica* at 620 nm absorption/reflection mode.

In the method applied here, peak corresponding to asiaticoside was symmetrical and well separated from other spots. The method was applied for the analysis of a

Fig. 2. Comparison of spectra of asiaticoside in the (1) standard and (2) sample tracks.

large number of accessions of *C. asiatica*. Results of a few are given in Table 1. All the results are average of three readings.

Table 1. Asiaticoside content in *C. asiatica* using HPLC and HPTLC

Accession no.	% Content of asiaticoside	
	HPLC	HPTLC
1	1.17	1.19
2	0.78	0.78
3	0.90	0.89
4	1.02	1.01
5	0.42	0.40

Experimental

The plant material *C. asiatica* was obtained from the experimental farm of this Institute at Lucknow and the voucher specimen deposited in the Gene bank of this institute.

Asiaticoside was isolated by column chromatography and confirmed by spectral analysis⁹.

Reagents and the HPTLC plates used were from E. Merck.

Analytical procedure :

For each determination the dried plant material (0.2 g) was extracted with methanol, filtered, defatted with hexane (3×10 ml) and the material obtained was redissolved in methanol (2 ml) for analysis.

Chromatography was performed on a preactivated

(110°) silica gel HPTLC plate $60F_{254}$ (10×10 cm). Samples and standards were applied to the plate as 6 mm wide bands with an automatic applicator under a flow of N_2 gas, 10 mm from the bottom, 10 mm from the side and the space between two spots 5 mm of the plate at a delivery speed of the syringe 10 s/ μ l. The application parameter were identical for all the analysis performed.

The TLC plate was developed in a CAMAG twin trough chamber which was presaturated with mobile phase ethyl acetate-methanol-water (60 : 12 : 8) for 1 h and the plate was allow to run for about 8 cm in the laboratory conditions of $25 \pm 5^\circ$ and 50% relative humidity. The composition of mobile phase was optimized by using different mobile solvents of varying polarity. After development, the plate was withdrawn, dried and spots were visualized by immersing the plate in vanillin-conc. sulphuric acid reagent using an automatic immersion device followed by heating of the plate at 110° for 10 min to visualize a blue coloured asiaticoside spot. Quantitative evaluation of the plate was performed in the absorption- reflection mode at 620 nm, using slit width 6×0.4 mm with a computerized CAMAG TLC scanner-3, CATS4 software version 3.14.

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